

**5th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
ON FOOD CONTAMINANTS:
CHALLENGES ON EXPOSURE ASSESSMENT,
HEALTH IMPACT AND SUSTAINABILITY OF FOOD SYSTEMS**

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

4-6 September, Campinas, Brazil

4 – 6 SEPTEMBER 2023
CAMPINAS, BRAZIL

CONFERENCE THEME
CHALLENGES ON EXPOSURE ASSESSEMENT,
HEALTH IMPACT AND SUSTAINABILITY
OF FOOD SYSTEMS

ICFC2023 BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

EDITED BY

Elsa Vasco, Sher Ali, Esther Paiva, Carlos Corassin,
Carlos Oliveira, Paula Alvito

Published by

Fundação de Estudos Agrários Luiz de Queiroz (Fealq)

Avenida Centenário, 1080 – Bairro São Dimas

CEP: 13416-000 – Piracicaba-SP

Telefone: + 55 19 3417-6600

fealq@fealq.org.br

Production services: Victor Benatti (@vbenatti)

Editorial support: Sônia Piacentini

Cover Designer: Nuno Alvito

September 2023: First edition

**Dados Internacionais de Catalogação na Publicação
DIVISÃO DE BIBLIOTECA - DIBD/ESALQ/USP**

International Conference on Food Contaminants: Challenges on Exposure Assessment, Health Impact and Sustainability of Food Systems (5 : 2023 : Campinas, SP)
Book of abstracts; 4-6 September 2023 Campinas, Brazil [electronic resource] / edited by Elsa Vasco ... [et al.]. -- Piracicaba : FEALQ, 2023.
194 p. : il.

ISBN: 978-65-89722-47-2

1. Contaminação de alimentos 2. Microbiologia de alimentos 3. Saúde pública
4. Segurança alimentar 5. Sistemas alimentares sustentáveis 6. Toxicologia de alimentos
I. Vasco, E., ed. II. Ali, S. ed., III. Paiva, E. ed., IV. Corassin, C. ed., V. Oliveira, C. ed.,
VI. Alvito, P. ed., VII. Título

CDD 614.31

Elaborada por Maria Angela de Toledo Leme - CRB-8/3359

Dear Participants,

On behalf of the National Institute of Health Doctor Ricardo Jorge (INSA), we are honored and delighted to welcome you to the 5th International Conference on Food Contaminants (ICFC2023) and to receive you in the beautiful city of Campinas/São Paulo (SP), Brazil.

The conference will be held, for the first time outside Portugal, at the Instituto Agronomico de Campinas (IAC) in Campinas/SP, Brazil, from 4 to 6 September, as a hybrid event (presential and online) to broaden the scope of this international conference and to contribute to a closer scientific cooperation between Portugal and Brazil. The ICFC2023 aims to promote contact with realities of different continents in the fields of exposure assessments of food contaminants, human health and sustainability of food systems.

Like many countries around the world, Brazil and surrounding neighbors from Latin America, reported relevant problems concerning food safety and security, difficulties related to the sustainability of food systems and their transformation and a scarcity of available data on human exposure to chemicals and associated health effects.

In addition, scientific knowledge on these topics needs to be shared between different regions and populations, and preferably, locally addressed, to provide effective support for policymaker's decisions that aim to protect human health and the environment. Therefore, ICFC2023 represents a unique opportunity to debate different ideas, methods, and approaches on food contaminants and human health, towards desirable and sustainable food futures.

We wish you an excellent Conference!

Fernando de Almeida

Chairman of the Executive Board of the
National Institute of Health Doctor Ricardo Jorge, I.P.
ICFC2023 Honorary President

Conference Chairs

Carlos Oliveira

(FZEA/USP, Brazil)

Paula Alvito

(INSA, Portugal)

Board Members

Adriana Pavesi Arisseto Bragotto

(UNICAMP, Brazil)

Adriano Gomes da Cruz

(SBCTA, Brazil)

Artur Alves

(CESAM, UA, Portugal)

Carlos Humberto Corassin

(FZEA/USP, Brazil)

Cristina Abreu Santos

(INSA, Portugal)

Elsa Reis Vasco

(INSA, Portugal)

FZEA/USP – Faculty of Animal Science and Food Engineering, University of São Paulo; INSA – National Institute of Health Doctor Ricardo Jorge; UNICAMP – University of Campinas; SBCTA – Brazilian Society for Science and Food Technology; CESAM – Centre for Environmental and Marine Studies; UA – University of Aveiro.

Scientific Committee

Adriana Pavesi Arisseto Bragotto (UNICAMP, Brazil)

Adriano Gomes da Cruz (SBCTA, Brazil)

Ana Gago-Martinez (University of Vigo, Portugal)

Anderson de Souza Sant'ana (UNICAMP, Brazil)

Artur Alves (CESAM, UA, Portugal)

Carlos Augusto Fernandes de Oliveira (FZEA/USP, Brazil)

Carlos Humberto Corassin (FZEA/USP, Brazil)

Elsa Reis Vasco (INSA, Portugal)

Isabelle Oswald (INRAE, France)

Jacob van Keveren (RIVM, The Netherlands)

Maria João Silva (INSA, Portugal)

Paula Alvito (INSA, Portugal)

Sarah de Saeger (University of Ghent, Belgium)

Susana Loureiro (CESAM, UA, Portugal)

UNICAMP – University of Campinas; SBCTA – Brazilian Society for Science and Food Technology; CESAM – Centre for Environmental and Marine Studies; UA – University of Aveiro; FZEA/USP – Faculty of Animal Science and Food Engineering, University of São Paulo; INSA – National Institute of Health Doctor Ricardo Jorge; INRAE – Institut National de la Recherche Agronomique; RIVM – National Institute for Public Health and the Environment.

The Organizing Committee would like to welcome all of you and express sincere appreciation for choosing the city of Campinas, Brazil, as the venue for the 5th International Food Contaminants Conference (ICFC2023).

The ICFC2023 is organized by a joint effort of researchers from the National Institute of Health Doctor Ricardo Jorge (INSA), from Lisboa and the Centre for Environmental and Marine Studies (CESAM) of the University of Aveiro, both from Portugal and the Faculty of Animal Science and Food Engineering (FZEA/USP), from Brazil. The ICFC 2023 also has the support of the Brazilian Society of Science and Food Technology (SBCTA) and the São Paulo Research Foundation (FAPESP). This three days conference is an international forum to gather researchers from different continents, to share and discuss their findings regarding the broad and interdisciplinary field of food contaminants under the theme “Challenges in exposure assessment, health impact and sustainability of food systems”.

Following the rationality on the impact of food contaminants on human health of ICFC conferences (ICFC2015 <http://hdl.handle.net/10400.18/3214>, ICFC2017 <http://hdl.handle.net/10400.18/4882>, ICFC-2019 <http://hdl.handle.net/10400.18/7166> and ICFC2021 <http://hdl.handle.net/10400.18/7795>), ICFC2023 will address the challenges related to the i) occurrence of food contaminants worldwide; ii) exposure assessment and health impact; iii) health, environment and sustainability of food systems and iv) networking and societal concerns of food contaminants.

Participants at this conference are cordially invited to contribute with a full manuscript to the Special Issue on “Chemical Contaminants in Foods: Exposure Assessment, Health Impact & Sustainability of Food Systems” on Food Research International.

Throughout this conference, we hope to create an atmosphere where everyone, academia, professionals and students, can exchange ideas and establish collaborations.

We look forward to welcoming and hosting you in Campinas and hope this conference becomes an unforgettable moment.

Carlos Oliveira and Paula Alvito
Chairs of ICFC2023

P33 – Elemental profiling and health risk of Serbian orange wines

Torović, L.j.^{A,B}; Lukić, D.^B; Milovanović, L.j.^C; Majkić, T. ^C; Beara, I.^C

^AUniversity of Novi Sad Faculty of Medicine Department of Pharmacy, Novi Sad, Serbia

^BInstitute of Public Health of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia

^CUniversity of Novi Sad Faculty of Sciences Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Novi Sad, Serbia

ljilja.torovic@mf.uns.ac.rs

Keywords: Food safety; Lifetime Cancer Risk; Non-carcinogenic risk

Introduction: Orange wine is a type of wine made from white wine grapes where the grape skins stay in contact with the juice and supply coloring pigment, in contrast with conventional white wine production. The aim of the present study was to obtain elemental profiles of orange wines and to assess associated health risk.

Methodology: Elemental profiles (Be, B, Al, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, As, Se, Sr, Mo, Cd, Sn, Sb, Te, Ba, Hg, Tl, Pb) of 24 bottled orange wines were obtained using ICP-MS. Adult men and women exposure was estimated taking into account wine consumption on population average, regular drinkers only and chronic heavy drinkers, according to the World Health Organization data, as well as Serbian food consumption survey.

Results: The study revealed rather versatile elemental profiles, but not one indicating potential for non-carcinogenic risk (all samples had hazard indices below 1, with maximum at 0.44) in any of the consumption scenarios. Both mean and high (last quartile mean) level of margin of exposure (MOE) associated to lead nephrotoxicity were over 10, for men, women and both sexes together. The lowest MOE was obtained for highly exposed males (consumers only – national consumption data, MOE 11). With regard to carcinogenic risk of arsenic, MOE approach indicted no risk (minimum MOE 20). Conversely, lifetime cancer risk approach showed that tolerable risk of 1 extra lifetime cancer case per 100,000 persons was exceeded across the exposure scenarios, by up

to 9 (men), 6 (women) and 8 (both sexes) wine samples. However, risk corresponding to mean exposure was acceptable, while high level of exposure resulted with increased risk for chronic heavy drinkers and consumers only, both men and women.

Conclusion: Orange wines are still relatively rare in Serbia and there is a lack of data related to their quality and safety. Elemental composition is influenced by endogenous sources, conditions of grape growth and winemakers' interventions and multi-element profiling could contribute to wine differentiation in terms of geographical origin. No less important, certain elements influence sensory properties of wine.